

Test results for gradients, geometry optimizations, and Hessians in solutions with the PTED coupling scheme

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1 Intro

This data publication contains data that was used to verify the numerical correctness of the analytic gradients implemented for all the methods available in the grad, rdgrad, and ricc2 programs of the TURBOMOLE package (HF, DFT, MP2, and CC2 for ground states, CIS, ADC(2), and CC2 for excited states) with the implicit solvent models:

COSMO using TURBOMOLE’s internal implementation with the Gaussian Charge Model (GCM, option gauss)

EC-RISM using TURBOMOLE’s interfaces to the RISMpar program developed at TU Dortmund, using for the long range potential (`lrtype`) the options `-8` or `-5` with the closures PSE-1, PSE-2, or PSE-3.

For all post-HF wavefunction models or excited-states the PTED coupling scheme as described in J. Phys. Chem. A, 129, 6155-6169 (2025) is used. The results reported here go beyond what is described in the latter publication for COSMO and a similar publication on

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EC-RISM (Implementation of EC-RISM of ADC(2) and CC2 to Include Solvent Granularity Effects in Excited-State Energies and Gradients, J. Haberhauer, Patrick Kibies, Stefan M. Kast, and Christof Hättig, in preparation) by extending it to the calculations of molecular Hessians and vibrational frequencies in solution. These are evaluated by numerical differentiation of the analytic gradients with TURBOMOLE’s script `NumForce`. For this, the scripts `NumForce`, `cc2cosmo`, `cc2ecrism`, and `runsingle` have been adapted so that `cc2cosmo` and `cc2ecrism` can be used by `NumForce` and `runsingle` to obtain (after self-consistent equilibration of the density with the reaction field) the analytic gradients and dipole moments of the equilibrated reference state.

2 Technical Note

For EC-RISM, the current work uses for the electrostatic interaction TURBOMOLE’s implementation of analytic gradients reported in “Implementation of EC-RISM of ADC(2) and CC2 to Include Solvent Granularity Effects in Excited-State Energies and Gradients”, by J. Haberhauer, Patrick Kibies, Stefan M. Kast, and Christof Hättig, (*in preparation*) and for the LJ interaction the analytic gradients evaluated in the RISMpar program.

TURBOMOLE’s implementation of the solvent potential and the gradients for the electrostatic interaction assumes for the environment and its potential a finite non-periodic rectangular box, identical with the box for the integration grid, while the RISM equations in RISMpar are solved using periodic boundary conditions with Ewald summation (`lrtype= -8`). For (`lrtype= -5`), RISMpar applies a switching function to the electrostatic potential in a boundary region close to the box boundaries and a correction term to the chemical excess potential to account for the difference between the non-periodic and periodic descriptions. TURBOMOLE’s interface to RISMpar only includes the correction to the chemical excess potential in the (free) energy of the solvated QM system, but evaluates the reaction field potential for the electrons and the electrostatic contribution to the analytic gradients without corrections. Mismatches between the electrostatic potentials at the left/right, top/bottom, or front/back faces of the integration box, interactions with the charge distributions from translational images of the solute with solvent shell, and all effects are neglected for `lrtype= -8`. For `lrtype= -5` also the influence of the potential switching is ignored. Thus, for EC-RISM calculations the analytic gradients become only fully consistent with numerical derivatives of the free energy in the limit of an infinitely large box size. This is true for `lrtype= -8` and `lrtype= -5`.

The COSMO implementation in TURBOMOLE does not use periodic boundary condition. With the Gaussian Charge Model used for the current tests, the analytic gradients are consistent with numerical derivatives of the free energy up to tiny contributions originating for non-symmetric molecules from incomplete rotational symmetry with a finite integration grid (similar as for DFT integration grids). The respective rotationally forbidden contributions are removed by projection.

3 Correctness check of the analytic gradients with 1-D PES scans

The spreadsheet `C1H.ods` contains of the diatomic molecule ClH comparisons between potential energy scans and the results obtained for the end points of geometry optimizations with the analytic gradients at the Hartree-Fock level. The tar file `C1H_Scan.tar` contains the output from and input files for the calculations that have been carried out to obtain the above results.

The results show that

- for COSMO the geometry optimization can be converged (with the default grid) to a gradient norm $< 10^{-6}$ a.u. and that the structure and the energy at the optimized geometry agrees with the results of the PES scan within $< 10^{-5}$ bohr for the bond distance and $< 10^{-9}$ hartree for the energy
- for EC-RISM there is a small dependence of the results and the agreement between PES scan and geometry optimization on the grid parameters: the larger the integration box and the smaller the step size the better is the agreement. Tight agreement requires large integration grids and small step sizes. There is also a tiny dependence of the agreement on the long range treatment (`lrtype`). The effect is small compared to that of the grid parameters. The results indicate that the geometry optimization with the analytic gradient implementation is with `lrtype = -5` slightly better in agreement with the point-wise computed PES than for `lrtype = -8`.

4 Geometry optimization for a polyatomic molecule

As example of a geometry optimization for a polyatomic molecule with a correlated wavefunction method and the fully self-consistent reaction-field coupling scheme, results for quinoline in aqueous solution are reported. The geometries have been optimized at the PTED-COSMO-CC2/def2-TZVPP and PTED-EC-RISM-CC2/def2-TZVPP levels of theory. For COSMO the Gaussian Charge Model with the default grid was used. The EC-RISM calculations were carried out with a box margin of 15 Å with a step size of 0.3 Å, the PSE-2 closure, and `lrtype = -8`. The results for the optimized stationary ground-state minima are:

COSMO CC2 free energy = -401.1117214581, norm of residual gradient: $|dE/dxyz| = 0.000071$

EC-RISM CC2 free energy = -401.0807185768, norm of residual gradient: $|dE/dxyz| = 0.000029$

All output files with the original data and the input file that where used to generate the data are contained in the tar archive `quinoline.tar`.

	PTED-COSMO			PTED-EC-RISM		
c	2.33167875726691	2.69400520460100	0.00006777757671	2.32661119729897	2.68607878083768	-0.00030807501582
c	4.54154970082326	1.31795413531163	0.00002642788828	4.53661576194490	1.31774796608993	-0.00002813914111
c	4.40139385026849	-1.34707761192914	-0.00002615751377	4.40381788772146	-1.33918511759366	0.00013103965428
n	2.25692887783834	-2.65555463239252	0.00005813763955	2.25586594249049	-2.63798997884694	-0.00001138266520
c	0.04834440046416	-1.30374942665583	0.00001810534246	0.04184914992718	-1.30305670393592	-0.00012336550206
c	-0.00575896926466	1.39724358862279	0.00000741030724	-0.00609815798079	1.39167327168057	-0.00015376117729
c	-2.36203420685791	2.66850361596137	-0.00003632040219	-2.35673160277815	2.66278590283301	0.00000964018544
c	-4.58652066929128	1.30847268754039	-0.00007725733877	-4.57875136319249	1.30674279277543	0.00014548831966
c	-4.53450952819891	-1.36400874263183	0.00003786195370	-4.52921361988214	-1.36121470635550	-0.00000267020111
c	-2.26402340785734	-2.64856177178729	0.00003368178199	-2.26400295273011	-2.64666663020228	-0.00018665121201
h	2.35131323736594	4.74241124131704	0.00019957866428	2.34301629633858	4.72937564738972	-0.00029705307717
h	6.36757861117998	2.23610767777250	0.00002733705506	6.35686687662666	2.23544376555679	0.00019370786099
h	6.13037495013485	-2.44760583741541	-0.00027041930618	6.12409066835264	-2.44239723150845	0.00042820809057
h	-2.38113867248306	4.71692307952939	-0.00002040171661	-2.37192290603240	4.70621542631381	0.00004609014811
h	-6.38323762196175	2.28551396700200	-0.00026589319408	-6.37046920465925	2.28294432522063	0.00038636088429
h	-6.29377233060519	-2.40754313744771	0.00017880132389	-6.28476732431740	-2.40169055621896	0.00012702681148
h	-2.19894563863402	-4.69415611965042	0.00004132993851	-2.20755530894035	-4.68792903628790	-0.00035646396301

5 Computation of Hessians and vibrational frequencies

PTED-COSMO-CC2			PTED-EC-RISM-CC2		
mode	wave number cm**(-1)	IR intensity km/mol	mode	wave number cm**(-1)	IR intensity km/mol
1	0.00	0.00000	1	-0.00	0.00000
2	0.00	0.00000	2	-0.00	0.00000
3	0.00	0.00000	3	0.00	0.00000
4	0.00	0.00000	4	0.00	0.00000
5	0.00	0.00000	5	0.00	0.00000
6	0.00	0.00000	6	0.00	0.00000
7	168.16	8.24199	7	147.04	9.80643
8	175.80	0.81577	8	173.14	1.62316
9	372.45	8.05472	9	370.60	7.61288
10	386.31	2.78256	10	388.40	2.91033
11	462.06	0.29834	11	459.08	1.92976
12	477.84	14.36429	12	479.92	11.27862
13	514.95	0.24306	13	514.79	0.05923
14	519.95	0.21002	14	518.79	0.49870
15	593.56	1.12833	15	598.39	2.40826
16	606.96	11.40604	16	598.80	10.40833
17	735.44	5.70782	17	739.11	12.76294
18	759.81	4.69556	18	761.55	3.09672
19	762.31	30.42891	19	771.12	25.87034
20	816.37	2.16187	20	817.92	0.51517
21	816.95	144.32649	21	825.30	145.15652
22	859.23	0.20047	22	864.66	0.02315
23	937.24	5.58644	23	935.30	0.15061
24	943.85	0.47074	24	953.03	1.90390
25	951.27	1.68471	25	960.03	1.62677
26	956.34	0.18427	26	963.79	0.77240
27	980.10	1.63122	27	989.30	1.96643
28	1029.98	8.81795	28	1035.98	11.81653
29	1051.96	2.50943	29	1062.85	4.17257
30	1126.92	15.82941	30	1130.92	9.89388
31	1150.52	1.83033	31	1158.41	1.92785
32	1161.48	1.65449	32	1168.71	0.62730
33	1238.43	0.91261	33	1247.49	4.77053
34	1253.73	4.32051	34	1260.96	3.50222
35	1270.77	1.67645	35	1278.50	6.32246
36	1377.35	22.41893	36	1389.85	24.05708
37	1408.03	7.08999	37	1419.11	8.09077
38	1425.42	8.92381	38	1434.91	14.09701
39	1459.32	6.02723	39	1469.30	1.29072
40	1477.68	4.65144	40	1484.93	9.76964
41	1528.84	59.08529	41	1540.38	69.56506
42	1579.53	18.11133	42	1594.01	25.18524
43	1605.08	16.17332	43	1614.52	10.12009
44	1642.22	11.09784	44	1651.79	17.23940
45	3185.86	20.12017	45	3216.86	6.44708
46	3192.18	3.28263	46	3219.51	12.28467
47	3197.13	4.60484	47	3226.12	6.07055
48	3203.00	0.79222	48	3229.67	0.97374
49	3215.47	12.71507	49	3240.81	32.15319
50	3225.28	15.18195	50	3249.91	16.28570
51	3229.92	8.31676	51	3258.65	9.96147

The calculations have been carried out for the ground-state of quinoline in the def2-TZVPP basis set. For COSMO the Gaussian Charge Model with the default grid was used. The EC-RISM calculations were carried out with a box margin of 15 Å with a step size of 0.3 Å, the PSE-2 closure, and `lrtype = -8`.

The vibrational spectra obtained with PTED-COSMO-CC2/def2-TZVPP and PTED-EC-RISM-CC2/def2-TZVPP for quinoline in aqueous solution in its electronic ground state are similar. The frequencies obtained with EC-RISM are for this example a bit higher than

for COSMO, probably as consequence of a stronger solvation of the lone pair at the pyridinic N atom.

All output files with the original data and the input file that where used to generate the data are contained in the tar archive `quinoline.tar`.